

THE ESSENCE OF MANAGING THE ACTIVITIES OF SPECIAL RECEPTION FACILITIES OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES FOR THE ADMISSION AND DETENTION OF ADMINISTRATIVELY ARRESTED PERSONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15697463>

The activities of special reception facilities for the admission and detention of administratively arrested persons in internal affairs bodies are distinguished by their specific nature. In particular, considering the volume and scale of work and its significance in implementing tasks to ensure the execution of court decisions imposing administrative arrest, this area is considered one of the main functions of the internal affairs bodies.

Current regulatory legal acts assign a number of tasks to special reception facilities intended for the admission and detention of administratively arrested persons. These tasks can be classified according to their nature as follows:

- organizing the admission and detention of administratively arrested persons;
- protecting the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of administratively arrested persons, as well as organizing the fulfillment of their assigned duties;
- implementing measures aimed at the social protection of administratively arrested persons;
- organizing interaction with state bodies and organizations, as well as civil society institutions, on collecting detention costs from administratively arrested persons and involving them in labor [1].

Studies indicate that the concept of managing special reception centers designed for the admission and detention of individuals subject to administrative arrest is not defined in any regulatory legal documents or research works.

In this regard, based on the analysis of legal literature, research works, and regulatory legal documents, we will attempt to define the concept of managing special reception centers intended for the admission and detention of individuals subject to administrative arrest.

It is known that the term "management" originates from the Italian word "managgiare." In many countries worldwide, management in the economic sphere is represented by the term "management," in the political sphere by "governance" (or "government"), and in the technical sphere by "control" (or "controlling").

As noted in legal literature, it is impossible to conceive of studying management in internal affairs bodies without understanding the meaning of the concept of "management." The possibility of developing a general definition of the concept of "management" is determined by the fact that management is inherent in any group activity of people. Management is an objectively necessary condition for the functioning of a particular social organism. Through management, the actions of individuals are coordinated and unified, tasks are resolved, and common goals are achieved [2].

Analysis of legal literature and scientific research reveals that there is no unified approach to the concept of "management," and various definitions have been proposed by authors and researchers in this regard. Specifically, M.Z. Ziyodullaev defines the concept of

"management" as "the influence exerted by the managing body (person - subject of management) on the managed bodies (persons - object of management), carried out within a particular system" [3]. R.R. Aliullov states that "Management is a collaborative activity, implemented where an objective need arises, and is the most crucial means of uniting employees' efforts to achieve socially significant goals in addressing these important tasks. In modern conditions, the importance of understanding management as a socially oriented, purposeful activity of people aimed at solving vital problems is increasingly growing." V.V. Likholetov notes that "Management is one of the oldest forms of human activity. It is a conscious activity through which people organize and utilize elements of the external environment - society, nature, and technologies. Therefore, management is human activity aimed at simplifying processes occurring in nature, technology, and society, eliminating their disorder, and bringing them to a new state, taking into account their development trends and environmental changes" [4]. L.N. Khabazina, S.G. Kochergina, and N.P. Zirayeva provide the following definition: "Management originates from cooperation to coordinate people's activities" [5].

In theory, the concepts of "management" and "management activity" carry different meanings. Various definitions of the term "management activity" have been presented in legal literature and by scholars who have conducted research in this field. Specifically, A.D. Ulyanov states that "management activity, in a broad sense, encompasses all elements of organizational work related to management: organizational structure, personnel, information support, planning, control, regulation, and accounting. In a narrow sense, management activity is associated with the preparation, adoption, and organization of the implementation of management decisions" [6]. Meanwhile, M.S. Agafonova and K.A. Beregovich propose that "Management activity is a non-standard professional activity, characterized by the primary and general tasks of collaboratively organizing the actions of others to achieve common goals and objectives, based on the principle of hierarchy" [7].

In this regard, V.N. Kurochkin provides a more comprehensive definition of "Management Activity," which can be agreed upon. According to him, "Management activity is carried out through a set of management processes, that is, targeted decisions and actions implemented by managers in a specific sequence and combination, consisting of the following stages: obtaining and analyzing information; developing and making decisions; organizing their implementation; monitoring, evaluating the obtained results, making adjustments, rewarding or punishing executors.

These processes develop and improve along with the organization, and they can be single-stage or multi-stage; temporary or long-term; complete or incomplete; regular or irregular; timely or delayed, primary or secondary" [8].

According to the regulatory legal acts governing the activities of special reception centers for the admission and detention of persons under administrative arrest, the management of special reception centers for the admission and detention of administratively arrested persons is defined as the daily and purposeful activity of the Minister of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the heads of the Main Internal Affairs Directorates of Tashkent city and Tashkent region, the heads of Internal Affairs Directorates of other regions, their deputies, and the heads of authorized departments (divisions) in this area [9].

It is evident that the aforementioned thoughts, considerations, and views do not fully reveal the essence of managerial activity. This is because the presented opinions only address

issues related to the organizational or tactical foundations of management. In our view, important aspects of management in this process, such as legal, personnel, and material-technical support of activities, have been overlooked.

Just as there are functions that determine the qualitative level among the many tasks performed by a management subject, legal literature states that the main purpose of special reception centers intended for admitting and detaining persons under administrative arrest is to educate individuals in the spirit of observing and respecting the law, as well as to prevent the commission of new offenses by the offender and other persons [10].

In the process of reforming the system of special reception centers of the Internal Affairs Directorate for admitting and detaining persons under administrative arrest, issues of improving management organization are of particular importance. This is because no internal affairs body can function at the required level if management mechanisms are not effectively organized [11]. Therefore, for the effective management of the activities of special reception centers of the Internal Affairs Directorate for admitting and detaining persons under administrative arrest, it is necessary to organize the available forces and resources, arrange their activities in accordance with modern requirements, and coordinate them.

Managing the activities of a specific system, including special reception centers designed for admitting and detaining individuals under administrative arrest, is a comprehensive endeavor encompassing various functions, forms, and methods. These elements essentially form the fundamental basis for managing the operations of special reception centers intended for the admission and detention of individuals under administrative arrest. In our opinion, it is appropriate to categorize them as follows:

1) Legal foundations of management - entails the organization and regulation of activities of special reception centers for admitting and detaining individuals under administrative arrest through normative legal acts;

2) Organizational and methodological foundations of management - involves providing information support for the activities of special reception centers intended for admitting and detaining individuals under administrative arrest, planning, making and ensuring the implementation of management decisions, analysis, accounting, control, evaluation, and providing methodological assistance;

3) Material and technical foundations of management - involves equipping special reception centers for admitting and detaining individuals under administrative arrest with modern buildings, transport, technical and communication facilities, software (technological) and work equipment that meet contemporary standards;

4) personnel management fundamentals - provides for the training, placement, retraining, and professional development of qualified specialist personnel for special reception centers designed for the admission and detention of persons subjected to administrative arrest.

Therefore, *the management of special reception centers for the admission and detention of persons subjected to administrative arrest by the Internal Affairs Bodies* is an administrative activity carried out by authorized state bodies and officials through legal, organizational-methodological, logistical, and personnel support for the operations of special reception centers designed for the admission and detention of persons subjected to administrative arrest by the Internal Affairs Bodies.

Footnotes/References:

1. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 734 "On Approving the Regulation on Special Reception Centers Intended for the Admission and Detention of Persons Subjected to Administrative Arrest" (September 18, 2017) // Collection of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2017, No. 38, Art. 1043.
2. Fundamentals of Management and Information-Analytical Activity in Internal Affairs Bodies: Textbook / I. Ismailov, D.S. Mukhamadaliyev, E.U. Azizov; editor-in-chief B.A. Matlyubov. - T.: Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2019. - 561 p.
3. Ziyodullayev M.Z. Improving the Management of Support Points of Internal Affairs Bodies: Monograph. - T.: Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2018. - P.279.
4. Likholetov V.V. Enterprise (Organization) Management: Textbook / V.V. Likholetov. - Chelyabinsk: Publishing Center of SUSU, 2021. - 279 p.
5. Khabazina L.N., Kochergina S.G., Ziryayeva N.P. Management of Municipal Institution Activities and Directions for its Improvement // Bulletin of the Russian University of Cooperation. 2019. No. 4 (38). - pp. 96-100.
6. Ulyanov A.D. Management Activity as a Scientific Category // Proceedings of the Academy of Management of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Russia. - 2018. - No. 4 (48). - pp. 108-112.
7. Agafonova M.S., Beregovich K.A. Management Activity: Its Features, Structure and Characteristics // Scientific and Methodological Electronic Journal "Concept." - 2017. - No. 2. - pp. 438-441. [Electronic resource]. - URL: <https://e-koncept.ru/2017/570086.htm>.
8. Kurochkin V.N. Course of Lectures on Organization Management: Textbook K93 / V.N. Kurochkin. - Zernograd: Azov-Black Sea Engineering Institute FSBEI HE Don State Agrarian University, 2019. - 195 p.
9. Instructions on the Organization of Special Institutions' Activities // Approved by Order No. 28 of the Minister of Internal Affairs (January 31, 2018).
10. Activities of Internal Affairs Bodies in Maintaining Public Order and Ensuring Security: Textbook / I. Ismailov, M.Z. Ziyodullaev, F.N. Shukurov, et al.; under the general editorship of Lieutenant General B.A. Matlyubov. - T.: Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2019. - 414 p.
11. Orlova Yu.Yu. The Essence and Content of Managerial Activities in the Bodies of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Russian Federation // Bulletin of Moscow University of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Russia. - 2014. - No. 3. - pp. 136-138.

